

SENSITIVITY TO LOUDSPEAKER PERMUTATIONS DURING AN EIGHT-CHANNEL ARRAY REPRODUCTION OF PIANO NOTES

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ABSTRACT

An experiment has been conducted, in which ten pianists with different skill rated the sound realism and scene accuracy of a sequence of piano notes reproduced by a linear loudspeaker array, whose channel positions were changed during the test so to define different spatial patterns for the same sequence. Only exaggerated channel permutations produced significant downgrade of both qualities, furthermore without introducing appreciable changes of the apparent listening position. These results suggest that an accurate multi-channel reproduction of the frontal waves may not be crucial for determining the perceived quality of a digital piano.

1. INTRODUCTION

The quality of a digital piano depends on every design aspect of the electronic instrument, and involves current makers in a complex process that typically requires several iterations along the development cycle. Even if optimal source sounds are at hand, such as the output from a modern physically-based model or an accurate recording of the pressure field taken in the proximity of the real instrument, nevertheless the recipes that are needed to correctly display these sounds to the pianist remain a matter of experience and craft. Particularly in the case of piano sound reproduction, the rendering systems that have been proposed to fill the distance between the source and the listening point represent a manifold family spanning the history of digital pianos, ranging from standardized loudspeaker configurations [1] up to more recent arrangements aiming in particular at increasing sense of depth [2].

Performers declare to be especially sensitive to changes in the sound coming from their instrument. On the other hand, the role and importance played by the auditory cues when a piano is perceived to sound different is not obvious. In a pioneering paper, Mary Cochran claimed the insensitivity of pianists to piano tone quality [3]. Galemba and Askenfelt showed that a group of expert pianists lost much of their recognition ability when listening to three different

pianos, even if they had been able to identify them easily and accurately during a previous performing task [4]. Recent literature marks the difference existing between playing as opposed to listening to a piano: such two activities would in fact lead the pianist to develop different impressions about the quality of the instrument [5, 6].

The proposed research considers a collection of accurate multi-channel recorded piano notes, that were presented to a group of pianists via a calibrated array of eight small loudspeakers. Distortions were introduced during the listening test by exchanging the output channels, and subjective impressions about the realism of the sound and the auditory scene were gathered along with the apparent listening position. Our analysis suggests that only the largest permutations, in a sense that will be defined later, cause significant corruption of both qualities furthermore without clear implications on the auditory scene description.

2. EXPERIMENT

The experiment was intended to pilot a broader research aiming at clarifying whether pianists, while listening to reproduced piano sounds in the inside of a normal room, are able to discriminate differences in the spatial-temporal envelope of the *partial* components forming each note: if proved to exist, this ability may concur to characterize the *apparent source width* [7] of the instrument, and hence be exploited to create auditory sense of depth and “spaciousness” similar to those pianists declare to experience when they play a real (especially grand) piano.

The evolution in space and time of such envelopes mainly depends on the radiation properties of the soundboard [8]. A linear array of small loudspeakers reproduces at least some patterns of radiation at a central listening point in front of the array, within a reasonably wide frequency range. For this reason, this system represents a solution for achieving sufficiently accurate reproductions of a piano soundfield in the performer’s listening area, at reasonable cost.

Before experimenting on the perception of differences in the reproduced partial components, we decided to first test whether a group of pianists was able to discriminate major distortions in the soundfield: did the subjects judge the distorted soundfields to be less consistent and/or to sound worse, then it could make sense to increase the precision of the reproduction and to focus the investigation on specific perceptual effects, and the cues at their origin. Rather, our experiment suggests that the pianists’ ability to discrimi-

Figure 1. Recording session: microphone setup.

nate a reproduced piano soundfield distortion in terms of perceived realism is lower than expected.

2.1 Stimuli

Six *mezzo forte* piano notes (C4, E4, C2, A4 major, D4, C5) were selected from a huge collection, result of a recording session made in July 2012 at the Viscount International SpA semi-anechoic room based in Mondaino (RN) - Italy, using a Seiler model 1849 piano that was tuned and prepared for the occasion, and then played by a professional pianist and sound designer consulting for the company. Such notes were collated together one after the other, hence forming a slow scale lasting about thirty seconds.

Fig. 1 illustrates the recording setup consisting of a linear array of 30 Bruel&Kjær model 4188 omnidirectional microphones, calibrated and made available by Angelo Farina's acoustics research group at the University of Parma, along with an M-Audio multi-channel sound interface. The array was positioned in such a way to capture the soundfield in front of the cover, which was left open.

The reproduction was realized avoiding any signal processing, by just reporting eight equally-spaced recorded channels onto a single-pressure chamber linear array made with 2.5" Ciare loudspeaker units, prepared by the same research group. The array was driven by four t.amp model S75 stereo power amplifiers. Before feeding such amplifiers, the frequency range below 60 Hz was cut in each channel by an 48 dB/octave linear phase digital filter, to prevent injection of energy in the low frequency in the respective loudspeaker; in parallel, the sound in the low frequency range was isolated using a complementary filter, accepting a downmix of the eight channels and then sending its output to a Mitsubishi 8" active woofer standing below the array. Note that the fundamental components of all notes forming the scale have a frequency above 60 Hz, hence none of them was mixed down into the woofer. Finally, the 8+1 output channels were played by Adobe Audition running on a desktop PC, which drove an M-audio Delta 1010 audio card.

Fig. 2 shows the alignment between the microphone and the loudspeaker array, with the piano keyboard taken as reference: the eight loudspeakers, hence, reproduced the

Figure 2. Microphone/loudspeaker alignment.

recorded channels no. 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20 and 22, respectively. From here on we will associate such recorded channels respectively to the loudspeakers 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, numbered left to right.

Ten reproduction patterns were prepared using the eight channels: two of them were formed respectively by quadruplicating two, and duplicating four recorded channels over the loudspeakers; the third one was left untouched; the remaining seven were obtained by permutations of the inputs. All patterns are listed in Table 1 below.

Pattern no.	Configuration	Label
1	11118888	Magnified stereophony
2	11336688	Magnified quadraphony
3	12345678	Original
4	21436587	Swapped adjacent ones
5	34127856	Swapped adjacent pairs
6	56781234	Swapped quadruples
7	73258146	Random no. 1
8	78345612	Swapped edge pairs
9	87654321	Reverse panning
10	51843276	Random no. 2

Table 1. Output patterns.

2.2 Subjects

Three professional pianists, four piano practitioners, and three amateur sound engineers having regular contact with the instrument were involved in the test, for a total of seven male and three female (age 13-49, avg 33.2 years old). All reported normal hearing ability and understood the Italian language. On a scale ranging 1 to 7 they declared sufficient (2) to excellent (7) knowledge of the instrument (avg 4.7).

2.3 Setup and method

The experiment was set up in a silent, dry room (approximately $3 \times 3 \times 2.75$ meters) having walls partially covered with damping foam. In addition to the active array, four loudspeakers were located each at one corner of the room, furthermore two additional eight-channel arrays were put in front of the listener: the presence of such idle systems added uncertainty in the listeners about the sources that were going to be used during the experiment.

Subjects had to sit on a chair at the center of the room, approximately one meter far from the loudspeaker array. While sitting, every subject was given a tabletop computer on which (s)he could respectively rate the *realism of the*

Figure 3. Graphical user interface used for the tests.

sound R_S and the realism of the auditory scene R_A on a scale ranging 1 (poor) to 7 (excellent), as well as choose his or her own relative position R_P in the virtual scene among nine possible listening points, labeled A to I in alphabetical order (see Fig. 3). Before the test, the subject was given verbal instructions about the scale (s)he was going to listen to, as well as about the use of the graphical interface.

The test consisted of listening to a balanced random distribution of the patterns, each repeated five times for a total of fifty trials. During each trial, every subject listened to the musical scale and then rated R_S , R_A and R_P by selecting the corresponding value in the graphical interface; finally, (s)he submitted her or his selections by pushing a software button. After each submission a new trial was started: this procedure allowed in particular for rating a scale and go to the next one by submitting before the end of the current sound, or conversely to pause at the end of a trial by delaying the respective submission. In this way subjects could optimize the flow of the test, which took approximately 40 minutes to be completed.

3. RESULTS

Fig. 4 (above) plots, for each pattern in the respective box, the median of the corresponding rate R_S , the 25th and 75th percentiles with their extreme datapoints, the average values and the outliers. The same boxes are displayed for each pattern rated R_A , below in the figure. Both plots have been

Figure 4. Boxplots showing median, 25th and 75th percentiles with their extreme datapoints, average values ('o') and outliers ('+') for each output pattern rated R_S (above) and R_A (below), respectively. On either boxplot, the rectangle in dashed line gathers average values within the respective HSD range, edged by the largest average.

obtained using the `boxplot` function of Matlab.

An informal inspection suggests the existence of a significant decay in both sound and scene realism when the patterns 7,8 and 10 are displayed. In fact, significant differences in the average subjective rates exist among patterns, concerning in general the perceived realism of both sounds (repeated-measures anova: $F(9,81) = 8.2056$, $p = 1.44e-8$) and auditory scenes (repeated-measures anova: $F(9,81) = 6.9137$, $p = 2.50e-7$). However, only relatively few pairs are actually responsible for such differences: concerning sound realism, a Tukey's HSD value amounting to 1.048 has been computed; concerning the realism of the scene, we obtained a Tukey's HSD value amounting to 1.031. Essentially these results confirm the eye inspection of Fig. 4, in which we have added a rectangle in dashed line in either boxplot, grouping averages within the respective HSD including the largest value: even if such rectangles do not strictly split the respective averages in two categories based on the significance of their paired differences — compare for instance patterns 1 and 7 in both boxplots — never-

theless they give a useful picture about the significance of most paired comparisons.

The apparent listening positions exhibit a broad spectrum of selections, that are summarized in Fig. 5. Also on the light of the significance observed regarding the realism of the auditory scene, no statistical analysis of such apparent positions has been attempted: their dependence on the output pattern is instead left to the reader’s qualitative inspection of the same figure, and will be informally discussed in the next section.

Some subjects showed large deviations around their average ratings, at least for some patterns. Concerning sound realism, the largest std values across subjects respectively amounted to 1.79, 2.35, 1.0, 1.48, 1.79, 2.83, 1.95, 1.58, 0.89, 0.54; within subjects, the same values amounted to 2.05, 2.30, 2.30, 1.64, 1.67, 1.94, 1.73, 2.83, 2.34, 1.73. Similar ranges were found for the realism of the scene. During the final debriefing, all subjects expressed positive surprise for the unexpected quality of the multi-channel sound reproduction, and consequent satisfaction for their participation in the experiment.

4. DISCUSSION

The first consideration concerns the perceived realism of the sounds. Perhaps surprisingly, listeners did not judge the realism as significantly lower but for few patterns. A deeper look to Fig. 4 suggests that the random distributions of the output channels were judged to form kind of “worst category” in terms of sound realism. Pattern 8 suffers from a lower average rating as well: this evidence may depend on the higher degree of distortion coming from swapping the edge pairs of the multi-channel output.

This consideration is reinforced by the results on the perceived realism of the auditory scene, in which patterns 7, 8 and 10 again show significant differences against the other stimuli. Together, both results suggest that listeners may correlate the realism of the sounds with the realism of the auditory scene, and, perhaps, downgrade both of them once a distortion threshold is reached.

To quantify this idea in simple terms, we have computed a figure of penalty P_i for each pattern $i = 1, \dots, 10$. The penalty value is obtained by summing up nine “scores of neighborhood”, one for each pair of subsequent loudspeakers in the array, based on the following rule: a loudspeaker pair scores zero if both speakers reproduce the same channel n ; otherwise the same pair scores $k - 1$, in which k is the distance between the reproduced channel numbers (e.g., the pair scores $k - 1$ if its speakers respectively reproduce the channels n and $n + k$, or $n + k$ and n). In particular, it follows that a score of neighborhood equals zero if the corresponding loudspeaker pair reproduces the same channel as well as two adjacent channels irrespectively of their orientation along the array. Based on this rule we can compute a penalty for each pattern, and obtain the list appearing in Table 2, which is in fairly good correspondence with the judgments on realism.

As a second consideration, let us instead consider the perceived similarities among patterns. How can it be that pianists declare to be so sensitive to the piano sound qual-

i	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
P_i	6	4	0	6	5	6	16	8	0	15

Table 2. Pattern penalties.

ity and the related auditory scene during playing, and conversely our group on average failed in discriminating the realism of most multi-channel presentations once the order of such channels was changed in the array?¹ An inspection channel-by-channel (see Fig. 6) of the temporal envelopes of the fundamental, first and second partial component of the note C4 used for the stimuli, computed by processing every channel of the array with a bank of heterodyne filters each fitted on a partial component by means of a dynamic programming search algorithm [9,10], shows the existence of local relative differences among the envelope amplitudes amounting to 20 dB and more. Switching such components among channels should translate in appreciable changes of the resulting soundfield.

At least two arguments can be attempted to support this relative insensitivity of our group to loudspeaker permutations in the array. i) A professional pianist who is asked to evaluate a novel instrument definitely prefers to play instead of simply listening to it: only if engaged in an interactive task does the performer feel him or herself sufficiently confident as an evaluator. It is possible that most variations in the soundfield that were presented during the experiment cannot be perceived by pianists, as far as they are engaged in a passive listening task. ii) We speculate that our subjects had specific listening practice with their own piano, conversely they were not used to judge sounds coming from an unknown instrument. Both arguments do not contradict rigorous studies, investigating on the perceived acoustics of a piano made through listening as opposed to performance tests, especially concerning judgments on its tone and touch quality [5,6].

The conclusions about the relative insensitivity of pianists to loudspeaker permutations may be further supported by the wide scope of apparent listening points (see Fig. 5) subjects selected during the test. The breadth of this scope is almost certainly also a result of the known tendency of subjects to make, during a test, multiple choices from a palette of possible answers when the stimuli actually do not bring significant information for that choice. Mainly due to this suspicion, the blocks in Fig. 5 hardly establish any significance. However, some considerations are worth being done: i) pattern 1 seems to establish a polarization around the “I” position, that is, the center of the instrument. This fact does not contradict the stereophonic nature of the corresponding stimulus, and the existence of phase cancellations among identical components reproduced by multiple speakers, hence the possible net loss of spatial cues otherwise present in the other stimuli; ii) the random patterns, i.e. 7 and 10, seem to evoke relative positioning of the piano off the frontal plane. This fact fits with the decreased

¹ This evidence does not imply that pianists did not detect *relative* differences among patterns. However measurable using a different experimental procedure, at present their discovery would have provided few insight for reproduction system design purposes.

Figure 5. Apparent listening positions as functions of the output pattern.

Figure 6. Temporal envelopes, channel-by-channel, of the fundamental (left plot), 1st partial (center plot), and 2nd partial (right plot) component of the note C4 used for the stimuli.

perceived realism of the auditory scene; finally, iii) reversing the output positions in the array (pattern 9) apparently does not translate in a significant impression of listening to the piano from its back (i.e., from positions “D”, “E” or “F”): this point is further commented in the next paragraph.

The perceived realism obtained by reversing the array points to a discussion about the ability of pianists to perceive the direction of arrival of a piano note. Traditional studies in the field have investigated the question limitedly to the stereophonic or binaural reproduction of piano sounds, furthermore considering the instrument as a concentrated sound source [12–14]. Even if stereophonic panning has been used in digital pianos to lateralize the notes based on the key/hammer position, and the interactive rendering of piano sounds through headphones is nowadays object of more advanced studies [11], nevertheless in a real piano only the initial noise of the key and hammer mechanics before the strike, responsible for the creation of the so-called *touch precursor* [15], may provide sufficient lateralization cues to a listener sitting in front of the keyboard: the following mechanical energy in fact is distributed across the bridge, soundboard and keybed while radiating from the instrument. The observation of a 10 ms temporal window containing the signal attacks for the note C4, see Fig. 7, suggests that the relative delays and amplitude differences among channels are not large enough to

elicit lateralization cues. On the other hand, should such cues be present in the sound then their reversal along the array would have created confusion in listeners who, conversely, in their answers neither downgraded the realism of the corresponding auditory scene nor polarized the apparent listening point toward the back of the instrument.

Similarly to the explanation given for motivating the stability of the perceived realism in presence of loudspeaker permutations in the array, independently of the existence of a precedence effect we conjecture that the localization of a note during playing is locked to the corresponding key position by the somatosensory cues of hand proprioception. Holding this locking effect, then the same position can be robustly recalled during listening: this previously learnt process may suppress the auditory localization of the same note via lateralization cues, in particular resolving any potential incongruence between the proprioceptive and auditory information. All this said, a rigorous discussion of the apparent listening points emerging from the tests appears to have limited consistency here, and should rather be reinforced through future experimentation.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research may support decisions of digital piano makers, who are often challenged by the idea

Figure 7. Temporal windows (10 ms) containing the attack of C4 on each channel.

of increasing the number of frontal output channels as a mean for improving the sound of their products. Holding some methodological immaturity as with many pilot studies, in the limit of its findings this paper suggests that such an option, and the consequent increase in hardware costs, must be pondered carefully. Besides this qualitative conclusion, the experiment leaves questions open concerning its repeatability over broader pitch and dynamic ranges, and across different subjective impressions. The scalability of the results to different array sizes and technologies should be dealt with as well. More in general, the exact nature of the auditory cues linking the objective to the perceived accuracy of a multi-channel piano reproduction is still largely unexplored.

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